

Support stakeholders on Carbon Capture Utilisation and Storage of ETIP ZEP and IWG9

Deliverable 5.2 Data Management Plan

Support stakeholders on Carbon Capture Utilisation and Storage of ETIP ZEP and IWG9

This is a Horizon Europe project (Coordinated and Support Action) funded by the European Union for 3 years (from 1 July 2022 until 30 June 2025).

Project summary

Support Stakeholders on Carbon Capture Utilisation and Storage of ETIP ZEP and IWG9.

The overarching goal of this project is to bring together and further develop a strong inclusive network of CCUS stakeholders – effectively interconnecting and coordinating the activities of CCUS European Technology Innovation Platforms (ETIP ZEP) and the CCUS SET Plan Implementation Plan Working Group (IWG9) – to support the development and implementation of the SET Plan.

Supporting the alignment and efficient coordination of stakeholders – including industry, researchers, public authorities, civil society – in order to accelerate the delivery of the CCUS research and innovation (R&I) activities and to progress the emerging policy priorities at EU and national level for the implementation of CCUS, will be crucial over the coming years for Europe to reach the ambitious climate targets for 2030 and 2050.

This will be achieved by efficiently aligning and coordinating the activities of ETIP ZEP and the IWG9 in a joint work programme; establishing networks and other fora to enable the stakeholders to collaborate and coordinate effectively, pooling expertise, experience and resources to address common challenges; engaging also with other programmes and external stakeholders; facilitating engagement and creating greater interaction and cohesion between the different CCUS activities; supporting the CCUS community to develop clear strategies and recommendations; accompanied by a strong continuous programme for outreach, dissemination and communication.

Disclaimer

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the authors only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union. The European Union cannot be held responsible for them.

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1. DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN

D5.2 Develop data management plan for the Pilot on Open Research Data (Month 5).

The Data Management Plan contains the relevant information required for the operational planning, execution, progress reporting and follow-up of the project.

2. DATA SUMMARY

This project – ‘Support stakeholders on Carbon Capture Utilisation and Storage of ETIP ZEP and IWG9’ – will not generate the type of research data (that might be expected with other types of research and innovation activity), for which a Data Management Plan will be needed.

The project will not bring new research data, however, it is based on full transparency. The project will collate data to illustrate policy or technological issues that impact CCS and CCU. Meetings and seminars are open, and all documentation, reports, papers, results, dissemination and communication will be made freely available to all interested parties via a dedicated project website as a continuous part of the project during its lifetime. Data contained in the documentation, reports, papers etc. will be comprehensively referenced to ensure that users can interpret and verify the conclusions of the project. Together with the stakeholders, a long-term repository for the information will be identified to ensure that the information is available beyond the period of the project.

The project will collect information on relevant European, national and industrial research and innovation activities that impact on CCS and CCU. This data will typically be collected in Word and Excel formats and be stored in SharePoint.

The project will handle company personal data/data of group members (referring to the government structure) in order to allow the project to effectively coordinate with the stakeholders. Personal data will only be processed in relation to specific purposes after considering and ensuring that privacy rights are not impacted, and where consent has been given to:

- provide newsletters and other updates
- provide information about upcoming events.

The origin of the data is information either already in the public domain or provided voluntarily by anyone who engages with the project. The size of the data is generally small.

The data will be useful to those organisations who are interested in the development and deployment of CCS and CCU. These are expected to be European institutions, national governments, academic researchers and industrial companies.

3. DATA – FINDABLE, ACCESSIBLE, REUSABLE AND SECURE

- *Findable and accessible:* The data will be readily findable on the project’s website and keywords are used to make the data is easily findable. The data will be made freely available on the project’s website. The project will not share personal data with any third parties without prior consent (which any persons are free to withhold) except where they are required to do so by law.
- *Interoperability:* All collected data is expected to be interoperable.
- *Increase data re-use:* The publicly available data will be actively communicated and disseminated to encourage its re-use.

Data security: The project is using generally accepted standards of technology and operational security to protect personal data from loss, misuse, or unauthorised alteration or destruction. Data is stored in SharePoint.

The SSZEPIWG9 SharePoint site has the following security settings:

- Access level: Project members (write access) + SINTEF Energi employees (read access). Further access restrictions on specific folders could if necessary be enabled.
- Encryption with SSL/TLS protects data transfer between partners and the SharePoint site.
- Threat management, security monitoring, and file-/data integrity prevents and/or registers possible manipulation of data.

Documents and elements in the SharePoint sites are stored in Microsoft's cloud solutions, based in Ireland and the Netherlands. There will be no use of data centres in the US or outside EU/EEA and associated countries¹.

Nightly back-ups are handled by SINTEF's IT operations contractor. As a baseline, all project data will be stored for 10 years according to SINTEF's ICT policy, unless otherwise agreed in contracts and data processing agreements.

Ethical aspects: There are no ethical issues associated with the project.

¹ EEA = Norway, Iceland, Liechtenstein